

Awareness, acceptability, congruency, and attainability of an academic institution's vision, mission, goals, and objectives

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Article Info

Article history:

Received Mar 28, 2023

Revised Jun 14, 2023

Accepted Jul 3, 2023

Keywords:

Attainability

Awareness and dissemination

Congruency

Understanding and

acceptability

Vision, mission, goals, and

objectives

ABSTRACT

The mandate of Isabela State University is to deliver higher learning in the arts, agriculture, natural sciences, technology, and specialized disciplines. Hence, the institution executes a strategic vision, mission, goals, and objectives (VMGO) to meet the expectations of its stakeholders. This research examined the degree of stakeholders' awareness, acceptance and understanding of the Isabela State University, College of Business, Accountancy, and Public Administration's (ISU-CBAPA) VMGO; its congruence with the educational approaches of the faculty and resources of the institution in delivering quality education; and whether the program goals and objectives of the business programs were attained. A quantitative descriptive research method was used. The results indicate that the respondents are generally highly aware of the ISU-CBAPA VMGO and its dissemination. The respondents perfectly understand and accept the ISU-CBAPA VMGO and highly perceive the extent of its congruence with academic strategies, practices, and activities. In addition, all respondents perceived that the ISU-CBAPA VMGO is being realized and favorably attained, despite the significant differences found. Recommendations include intensifying VMGO dissemination to external stakeholders, emphasizing VMGO commitments toward its realization, and emphasizing improvement on the students' development of professional skills, research capabilities, and competencies, and their readiness for employment and/or managing a business.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The Isabela State University (ISU) is guided by its vision and mission which serve as its strategic compass in carrying out its mandated function as cascaded down to the goals of the College of Business, Accountancy, and Public Administration (CBAPA), and its various program objectives. In pursuit of continuous development and improvement of higher education institutions, planned organizational directions must consistently be assessed and in coordination with the stakeholders.

Extant academic research studies have identified the vision, mission, goals, and objectives (VMGO) as an academic institution's main pillars of the foundation governing its mandated function [1]–[11]. Vision is the ideal outcome for the organization and the world it intends to create while a mission statement is a written description of what an organization does, for whom, how, and why [12]. The vision and mission

statements are significant in outlining the progression of a university [4] as it characterizes the most significant steps to be taken or completed by the university's decision-makers [13]. ISU has set its vision to become "a leading research university in the ASEAN region." As its mission, ISU is "committed to develop globally competitive human, technological resources and services through quality instruction, innovative research, responsive community engagement and viable resource management programs for inclusive growth and sustainable development." These statements are considered declarations of commitment a higher education institution (HEI) [14], [15], and vital in informing potential clients about the university's services and serve as both a guide and a standard for any organization that aspires to put policy into reality [16].

Likewise, a college or academic unit aligns its goals with its defined vision and mission statements to strengthen the numerous services given, conduct research and extension, and sustain and enhance operations [3]. This is consistent with Castillo [1] who emphasized the importance of ensuring that the objectives of each academic department are in line with the overall strategic vision and mission of the institution. Furthermore, the vision and mission must be consistent with the objectives of the various departments and their respective programs [1]. A high level of congruence of academic activities and practices to the VMGO implies that an academic institution is on the right path in achieving its targets [17]. The VMGO statements should be the main anchor of an institution's operations [18]; steering the organization with clarity and focus [8]; providing everyone with shared purpose [4]; guiding towards its intended direction [10], [19]–[21]; propelling everyone to advance at a similar pace and follow a path in performing its mandated function [4].

Moreover, setting an intended direction for an institution should not be merely espoused as declarations of commitment, but requires stakeholders' commitment for its realization which begins with the awareness and acceptability of the VMGO [10], [21]. Hence, such awareness and acceptability should encompass all members of the organization. However, stakeholders' familiarity may vary depending on the organizational unit they belong to. Those who have a direct relationship with the college or a specific academic unit, such as faculty and students, may possess a greater familiarity with college-based goals and objectives. This is because the individuals who are involved in the university's operation and administration have their own distinct set of goals and objectives that they must achieve. For instance, the staff and support services are focused on administrative roles, managing libraries, servicing laboratories, and assisting faculty and students in developing a learning culture [22] which are generally university-wide in scope and not confined solely to a specific college or program only. Still, studies have shown that staff and administrators have the highest level of awareness when it comes to the goals and program objectives [10], [17], [19]. Nevertheless, to attain the VMGOs, all stakeholders involved in an institution's operations must be aware as well as fully understand its implications [5]. They must be cognizant and recognize the institution's VMGO and believe that these statements are consistent and clearly stated; aligned with present academic practices or activities; and attainable to do their tasks more efficiently [23].

The primary aim of ISU-CBAPA is to provide students with the essential conceptual, human, and technical knowledge, skills, and competencies required for their multifaceted roles as future professionals. Therefore, VMGO attainability can be focused on educational strategies, practices, and activities provided by the university's academic and other support services. These approaches are evident in the program's emphasis on developing professional expertise, research capabilities and competencies; and preparing students for employment and/or managing a business. Institutional evaluation encompasses the assessment of various key result areas, including research productivity and quality of teaching [24]. Since, it is the goal of the university is to build its research reputation as stated in its vision, internal stakeholders in particular are enjoined to deliver through outcomes such as increased research involvement, publications, presentations, article citations, and externally funded projects. Applying a research-based education which entails equipping students with both research-based knowledge and the ability to conduct their own research [25] may help achieve such a target. Along with university policies, support services, and facilities, faculty members play a crucial role in developing professional expertise as their competence can affect the quality of education received by the students [24]. It is imperative that faculty members receive training in designing suitable content and curriculum, as well as cultivate an interactive learning environment [26] such as implementing a learning model that encourages learners to act and engage in teamwork processes [27] to facilitate both personal and professional growth. Faculty members also play a valuable role especially in the students' preparation and transition towards employment [28] by including career-related concepts in the curriculum design [29] and honing their personality traits [30]. Moreover, student-faculty interactions can influence students' self-perceptions of employability and graduate outcomes [26]. Essentially, enhancing students' academic and analytical skills, as well as their interpersonal and situational coping mechanisms can significantly impact the university, particularly in accomplishing its strategic aspirations [31].

Citing the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) CMO No. 46 S. 2012 Art. IV, Sec. 17, because VMGO statements are constructed with the institution's strengths and limits, as well as the needs and

opportunities in their locations, in mind, HEIs may uncover a variety of quality attributes and remarkable outcomes through commitment toward their VMGO [32]. In addition, a study [33] highlighted the significance of an institution's VMGO in its overall academic performance as a measure of the quality it delivers. Moreover, HEIs are often subjected to accreditation procedures. State universities and colleges (SUCs) undergo independent program reviews performed by the Accrediting Agency for Chartered Colleges and Universities in the Philippines (AACCUP), which includes assessing an institution's own ability to attain their VMGO [6]. Through AACCUP, ISU's VMGO was regularly assessed for its attainability [34]. In fact, ISU has been undergoing such process for its programs since 1993 and found it to have significant impact on VMGO as efficiency indicators and have also led to improvements particularly in its operation [34]. The AACCUP considers the VMGO as the most important of all the 10 areas to be examined throughout the accrediting process since it serves as the foundation for the functioning of an academic institution [3], [10]. In essence, the realization of the VMGO validates everything that occurs in the university.

Fundamentally, an organization must continuously assess its own status and strategically implement improvements in areas requiring attention before conforming to any external evaluation. The study on VMGO is deemed to have substantial significance to ISU-CBAPA and its stakeholders in the fulfillment of its thrusts and mandate. Existing academic studies have mostly focused on VMGO awareness, understanding and acceptability [2], [5], [6], [9]–[11], [20], [21], [23], and only a few studies have included its congruence and attainability [1], [3], [8], [17], especially delving through institutionally targeted purposes [33].

The current study was conducted to evaluate the activities, programs, and strategies that were being implemented and aligned to achieving the vision, mission, goals, and objectives of the university. The key purpose is to ascertain the respondents' awareness, understanding, and acceptance, and awareness of the dissemination of ISU's vision and mission, CBAPA goals, and its various program objectives; how congruent the ISU-CBAPA VMGO are with the performed strategy, practices, and activities of the faculty members and the school in delivering quality education; and evaluate if the program goals and objectives of the business courses were attained. Furthermore, the study also sought to measure the VMGO attainability in terms of i) the development of professional expertise; ii) the development of research capabilities and competencies; and iii) readiness for employment and/or managing a business of students. The study's results offer a thorough reflective evaluation using stakeholder VMGO perspectives that can benefit academic officials, faculty members, and non-teaching staff who play crucial roles in implementing the university's VMGO. This can help ensure that their respective units and strategies are in line with the institution's intended trajectory.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

A quantitative descriptive research approach was employed to assess the stakeholder respondents' awareness, understanding and acceptability, as well as their perception as to the congruency to academic strategies, practices and activities and the level of attainability of the ISU-CBAPA VMGO. A total of 735 stakeholder respondents participated in this study. Student participants (602) were randomly chosen from the different business programs of CBAPA. Respondents from the CBAPA faculty (31), alumni (54), and non-teaching administrators and personnel (48) were purposively chosen. The AACCUP Revised Instruments and a modified version of the survey instrument [33] were the basis for the survey instrument employed in this research. SPSS was used to tabulate and analyze the gathered data. Frequencies, ranks, and weighted means were used in determining the awareness, analyzing the understanding, and evaluating the perceptions of the respondents on the congruency and attainability of the ISU-CBAPA VMGO. Significant differences were measured through ANOVA at 0.05 level of significance. With a Cronbach alpha coefficient of 0.85, the scale in the survey questionnaire category has good internal consistency. The Cronbach alpha coefficients showing the internal consistency of the survey instrument in this study were shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Internal consistency of survey instrument

Description	Cronbach's alpha	No. of items
1. Awareness of the ISU-CBAPA VMGO of various stakeholder respondents	.977	4
2. Awareness of the ISU-CBAPA VMGO dissemination of various stakeholder respondents	.941	6
3. Understanding and acceptance of the ISU-CBAPA VMGO by various stakeholder respondents	.977	4
4. Perceptions of various stakeholder respondents on ISU-CBAPA VMGO's congruency with academic strategies, practices, and operations	.982	6
5. Perceptions of various stakeholder respondents on ISU-CBAPA VMGO's attainability	.979	4
6. Perceptions of the various stakeholder respondents on attaining the ISU-CBAPA VMGO with regards to:		
a. Development of professional expertise	.962	8
b. Development of research capabilities and competencies	.985	5
c. Readiness for employment and/or managing a business	.971	5

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Level of awareness, acceptance and understanding of the stakeholders regarding the ISU vision and mission; the goals of CBAPA, and objectives of its various business course programs

Table 2 reveals the stakeholder respondents' knowledge of vision and mission statements, goals, and degree-specific objectives of ISU-CBAPA. As indicated, all stakeholder respondents generally were extremely aware of the vision and mission of the university, CBAPA goals and the objectives in their respective programs, except for the non-teaching who were moderately aware of the CBAPA goals and purposively not asked about the program objectives due to their limited involvement on that level.

Table 2. Stakeholders' awareness of the ISU-CBAPA VMGO

Item	Students n=602	DI	Alumni n=54	DI	Faculty n=31	DI	Non-teaching n=48	DI	Weighted mean	DI
1. Awareness of ISU vision	4.71	EA	4.53	EA	4.84	EA	4.73	EA	4.71	EA
2. Awareness of ISU mission	4.66	EA	4.5	EA	4.84	EA	4.75	EA	4.70	EA
3. Awareness of CBAPA goals	4.53	EA	4.5	EA	4.74	EA	3.9	MA	4.43	EA
4. Awareness of CBAPA program objectives which I belong	4.53	EA	4.44	EA	4.84	EA	n/a	-	4.61	EA
Overall mean	4.61	EA	4.49	EA	4.81	EA	4.46	EA	4.61	EA

Note: Descriptive interpretation (DI); 1 to 1.80: Not at all aware (NA); 1.81 to 2.60: Slightly aware (SLA); 2.61 to 3.40: Somewhat aware (SOA); 3.41 to 4.20: Moderately aware (MA); 4.21 to 5.00: Extremely aware (EA)

In terms of dissemination, as shown in Table 3, the stakeholders were extremely aware that the ISU-CBAPA VMGO is well disseminated and displayed in conspicuous areas. However, the faculty and non-teaching were moderately aware when it came to the dissemination of the ISU-CBAPA VMGO to its external constituents, i.e. various agencies, institutions, business industries, and the community. Moreover, Table 4 shows that the stakeholders perfectly understand and accept the ISU-CBAPA VMGO. The non-teaching personnel of the university, on the other hand, considered the goals of CBAPA to be slightly understandable and acceptable, which may be due to their limited participation in academic activities.

Table 3. Stakeholders' awareness of the ISU-CBAPA VMGO dissemination

Item	Students n=602	DI	Alumni n=54	DI	Faculty n=31	DI	Non-teaching n=48	DI	Weighted mean	DI
1. The VMGO is posted on bulletin boards and disseminated in many print media, including but not limited to, catalogs, brochures, manuals, and program invites.	4.34	EA	4.41	EA	4.97	EA	4.50	EA	4.55	EA
2. The VMGOs are posted on the building, in the classroom, and in other areas of the institution.	4.39	EA	4.41	EA	4.61	EA	4.35	EA	4.43	EA
3. The VMGO is announced on social media platforms and the official university and campus webpages	4.27	EA	4.39	EA	4.29	EA	4.13	MA	4.26	EA
4. The VMGO is widely circulated to a variety of agencies, business industries, institutions, and the general community.	4.37	EA	4.30	EA	3.77	MA	3.90	MA	4.08	MA
5. The professors and staff in student affairs discuss it during general assembly or orientation every semester.	4.33	EA	4.44	EA	4.71	EA	4.31	EA	4.42	EA
6. The professors include the VMGO in the course syllabus and discuss it in class.	4.70	EA	4.37	EA	4.65	EA	4.00	MA	4.40	EA
Overall mean	4.40	EA	4.39	EA	4.50	EA	4.20	MA	4.36	EA

Note: Descriptive interpretation (DI); 1 to 1.80: Not at all aware (NA); 1.81 to 2.60: Slightly aware (SLA); 2.61 to 3.40: Somewhat aware (SOA); 3.41 to 4.20: Moderately aware (MA); 4.21 to 5.00: Extremely aware (EA)

In the Philippines, studies on HEIs have generally shown favorable results on stakeholders' awareness of their respective VMGOs [1]–[11], [17]–[21], [23], [32], [33]. Awareness is one step towards the realization of the VMGO [10], [20], [21]. The results in Table 2 concur with previous study [4] and suggest that ISU-CBAPA, through the existence of strong VMGO, also provides its constituents with a feeling of direction toward a shared purpose, encouraging everyone to adhere correspondingly toward a similar path in performing its mandated function.

Furthermore, the VMGO may be effective based on its structure and dissemination [2], which may be achieved by the university's stakeholders through their awareness and full understanding of the VMGO and its implications [5]. Thus, the result in Table 3 has positive claims on the effectiveness of the VMGO to ISU-CBAPA stakeholders. However, in terms of their awareness on the ISU-CBAPA VMGO dissemination, the non-teaching respondents were also found to be the least aware among others. Generally, the various stakeholders perfectly understand and accept the ISU-CBAPA VMGO thus, supporting the previous findings [8] and suggesting a positive outlook for the realization of the university's thrusts and mandates [6]. Interestingly, the non-teaching respondents were highly aware of the ISU vision and mission, even in its dissemination, as well as perfectly accept and understand these statements as these are university-wide aim and purpose. This suggests that the non-teaching respondents have comprehensive knowledge of the university's overarching aspirations, as well as the requisite steps needed to achieve them [17].

However, at the college level (CBAPA) goals along with its program objectives, there appears to be a lower level of awareness, acceptance, and understanding among non-teaching personnel, which is inconsistent with the findings of [10], [17], but agrees with another study [19]. This may be attributed to the notion that individuals working in the university's operation and administration are not directly engaged in this level, with the exception of those staff members affiliated with the college who have distinct goals and objectives to achieve. In relation, the staff and support services were mostly focused on administrative tasks, managing libraries, and laboratory management which indirectly help achieve the vision of the university through service management and use of strategically important resources [22].

Table 4. Stakeholders' understanding and acceptance of the ISU-CBAPA VMGO

Item	Students n=602	DI	Alumni n=54	DI	Faculty n=31	DI	Non-teaching n=48	DI	Weighted mean	DI
1. Understanding and acceptance of ISU vision	4.68	PUA	4.65	PUA	4.81	PUA	4.71	PUA	4.71	PUA
2. Understanding and acceptance of ISU mission	4.66	PUA	4.67	PUA	4.81	PUA	4.71	PUA	4.71	PUA
3. Understanding and acceptance of CBAPA goals	4.61	PUA	4.59	PUA	4.77	PUA	4.17	SUA	4.54	PUA
4. Understanding and acceptance of CBAPA objectives of the Degree Program I belong to and the responsibility of achieving these objectives in my capacity	4.52	PUA	4.59	PUA	4.84	PUA	n/a	-	4.65	PUA
Overall mean	4.62	PUA	4.63	PUA	4.81	PUA	4.53	PUA	4.64	PUA

Note: Descriptive interpretation (DI); 1 to 1.80: Totally not understandable and unacceptable (TNUU); 1.81 to 2.60: Slightly not understandable and unacceptable (SNUU); 2.61 to 3.40: Neutral (N); 3.41 to 4.20: Slightly understandable and acceptable (SUA); 4.21 to 5.00: Perfectly understandable and acceptable (PUA)

3.2. Perception on the level of congruency between the ISU-CBAPA VMGO and the academic strategies, practices, and activities

Table 5 shows that the various stakeholder groups deemed the academic strategies, practices, and activities implemented to be highly aligned with the ISU-CBAPA VMGO and acknowledged that academic practices, strategies, and activities implemented by the faculty and students significantly, to a very great extent, contribute towards the attainment of the program outcomes. Though the group of non-teaching personnel considers that the operation of ISU-CBAPA is aligned only to a great extent which may be attributed to their level's limited involvement in the academic aspects. The university sees to it that the VMGO is achievable and attainable and that it can easily be embraced and implemented through different strategic teaching methodologies, practices, and activities so that students will be fully equipped with their skills and competencies, and that the other partner agencies and stakeholders can collaborate and cooperate in the attainment of such. The very high congruency to the VMGO suggests that the university is headed in the right direction toward its targeted outcomes [17]. This is also consistent with previous research [1] who asserted that the goal of each academic unit along with the objectives of the different programs must be aligned with the university's vision as well as its mission.

3.3. Attainment of ISU-CBAPA VMGO as perceived by the respondents

As revealed in Table 6, the stakeholders such as students, alumni, faculty, and non-teaching personnel perceived that the ISU-CBAPA VMGOs were attained to a very great extent. The high attainability results are consistent with the previous studies [3], [8]. Given that an academic institution's vision, mission, goals, and objectives serve as its guiding principles [19], these findings suggest that the respondents were fully governed by the ISU-CBAPA VMGO principles. The attainment of ISU-CBAPA VMGO was through

the different approaches in educational strategies, practices and activities given by the university through its services and faculty in the program which leads to the development of professional expertise, development of research capabilities and competencies, and readiness for employment and/or managing a business.

Table 5. Perceptions on ISU-CBAPA VMGO's congruency with educational strategies, practices, and activities

Item	Students n=602	DI	Alumni n=54	DI	Faculty n=31	DI	Non-teaching n=48	DI	Weighted mean	DI
1. Actual academic strategies, practices, and activities are congruent with the university's vision.	4.52	TVGE	4.48	TVGE	4.45	TVGE	4.31	TVGE	4.48	TVGE
2. Actual academic strategies, practices, and activities are congruent with the university's mission.	4.53	TVGE	4.46	TVGE	4.42	TVGE	4.33	TVGE	4.44	TVGE
3. Actual academic strategies, practices, and activities are congruent with the goals of CBAPA	4.51	TVGE	4.50	TVGE	4.45	TVGE	4.31	TVGE	4.44	TVGE
4. Actual academic strategies, practices, and activities are congruent with the objectives of the program where I belong	4.52	TVGE	4.50	TVGE	4.42	TVGE	4.25	TVGE	4.42	TVGE
5. Actual academic strategies, practices, and activities implemented by the university, faculty, students significantly contribute to the attainment of program outcomes.	4.49	TVGE	4.48	TVGE	4.35	TVGE	4.27	TVGE	4.40	TVGE
6. All ISU-CBAPA operations are based on its VMGO.	4.58	TVGE	4.50	TVGE	4.39	TVGE	4.17	TGE	4.49	TVGE
Overall mean	4.52	TVGE	4.49	TVGE	4.41	TVGE	4.27	TVGE	4.42	TVGE

Note: Descriptive interpretation (DI); 1 to 1.80: To no extent (TNE); 1.81 to 2.60: To a slight extent (TSLE); 2.61 to 3.40: To some extent (TSOE); 3.41 to 4.20: To a great extent (TGE); 4.21 to 5.00: To a very great extent (TVGE)

Table 6. Perceptions on ISU-CBAPA VMGO's attainability

Item	Students n=602	DI	Alumni n=54	DI	Faculty n=31	DI	Non-teaching n=48	DI	Weighted mean	DI
1. The vision of ISU is being realized	4.57	TVGE	4.54	TVGE	4.32	TVGE	4.40	TVGE	4.44	TVGE
2. The mission of ISU is being realized	4.56	TVGE	4.48	TVGE	4.35	TVGE	4.40	TVGE	4.44	TVGE
3. The goals of CBAPA are being achieved	4.53	TVGE	4.50	TVGE	4.29	TVGE	4.13	TGE	4.36	TVGE
4. The objectives of the CBAPA Program I belong to are being achieved	4.60	TVGE	4.54	TVGE	4.23	TVGE	n/a	-	4.44	TVGE
Overall mean	4.57	TVGE	4.52	TVGE	4.30	TVGE	4.31	TVGE	4.42	TVGE

Note: Descriptive interpretation (DI); 1 to 1.80: To no extent (TNE); 1.81 to 2.60: To a slight extent (TSLE); 2.61 to 3.40: To some extent (TSOE); 3.41 to 4.20: To a great extent (TGE); 4.21 to 5.00: To a very great extent (TVGE)

3.3.1. Development of professional expertise

Table 7 indicates the perception of the various stakeholders on attaining the VMGO through the development of professional expertise of the students and graduates. Generally, the students, alumni, and non-teaching personnel observe "to a very great extent" that the university does support the development of professional expertise, whereas faculty members view it a notch lesser than the others.

The university sees to it that through the implementation of its VMGO, it will support the development of the students' expertise in their degree of specialization through the enhancement of the personal and professional skills and competencies of the students. Additionally, it equips students with advanced knowledge and skills in a specialized field, enhances their expertise through professional specialization, and offers valuable professional experiences. Overall, the positive response of the respondents is consistent with the result [33] wherein the VMGO of Cagayan State University – Aparri Graduate School was also highly attained in terms of developing the expertise of students and graduates, thus further implying

the successful attainment of the mandated purpose of a HEI. However, it can be gleaned that the alumni have the highest regard in terms of the VMGO attainment through the development of professional expertise, which is inconsistent to some extent with previous findings [31]. Their findings indicate that ISU-CBAPA did not satisfy the highest expectations of BS Entrepreneurship graduates in terms of the training they received at the university, as it is only moderately applicable to their current professional endeavors. The faculty members may agree with the findings [31], given that their standpoint suggests that the VMGO statements are not fully met through the students' development of professional expertise. Moreover, the quality of education being provided is directly affected by the competencies and the educational attainment of the faculty [24]. Hence, the institution must be meticulous in their recruitment process and also encourage and support the continuous professional development of the faculty members as their interaction with students can affect graduate outcomes [26]. It is also imperative to consistently enhance the faculty members' proficiency in formulating suitable content and curriculum, while also cultivating an interactive learning atmosphere [26]. In addition, the attainment of the VMGO through this purpose may be further achieved by considering the learning model [27], which engages learners in active participation and teamwork.

Table 7. Stakeholders' perceptions on VMGO attainability through the development of professional expertise

Item	Students	DI	Alumni	DI	Faculty	DI	Non-teaching	DI	Weighted	DI
	n=602		n=54		n=31		n=48		mean	
1. ISU-CBAPA enhances the personal and professional skills and competencies of students	4.56	TVGE	4.43	TVGE	4.23	TVGE	4.42	TVGE	4.41	TVGE
2. ISU-CBAPA prepares students for professional practice with advanced knowledge and skills in a specialized field of study.	4.60	TVGE	4.44	TVGE	4.29	TVGE	4.50	TVGE	4.46	TVGE
3. ISU-CBAPA expands knowledge and skill sets along with professional specialization	4.56	TVGE	4.43	TVGE	4.32	TVGE	4.44	TVGE	4.44	TVGE
4. ISU-CBAPA provides professional experiences to students	4.59	TVGE	4.43	TVGE	4.30	TVGE	4.35	TVGE	4.42	TVGE
5. ISU-CBAPA provides students with additional seminars or training other than curricular offerings	4.55	TVGE	4.48	TVGE	3.97	TGE	4.33	TVGE	4.33	TVGE
6. ISU-CBAPA instills vigor in continuous personal and professional growth and development	4.57	TVGE	4.44	TVGE	4.19	TGE	4.48	TVGE	4.42	TVGE
7. ISU-CBAPA cultivates the potential of students to be experts in their field	4.60	TVGE	4.41	TVGE	4.10	TGE	4.40	TVGE	4.38	TVGE
8. ISU-CBAPA equips students with leadership and managerial skills to direct and influence others	4.57	TVGE	4.44	TVGE	4.06	TGE	4.38	TVGE	4.36	TVGE
Overall mean	4.57	TVGE	4.44	TVGE	4.18	TGE	4.41	TVGE	4.40	TVGE

Note: Descriptive interpretation (DI); 1 to 1.80: To no extent (TNE); 1.81 to 2.60: To a slight extent (TSLE); 2.61 to 3.40: To some extent (TSOE); 3.41 to 4.20: To a great extent (TGE); 4.21 to 5.00: To a very great extent (TVGE)

3.3.2. Development of research capabilities and competencies

The ISU-CBAPA attained its purpose of developing the research capabilities and competencies of students and graduates to a very great extent as shown in Table 8. These findings imply that the university based on its VMGO thrives to enrich and equips its clientele with research methodologies, statistics, and research writing while promoting the culture of research and creative works by offering business research, feasibility studies, and business plan as part of their coursework. Research productivity is one of the key result areas evaluated in an institution [24]. As stated by Poliden and Bela-o [3], a college or academic unit, that aligns its goals with its defined vision and mission statements, strengthens the numerous services offered, conducts research and extension extensively, and sustains and enhances operations. Since the goal of the university is to build its research reputation as stated in its vision, it strives to cultivate and develop students in research-related activities which they can use in their future professional pursuits. It is noteworthy that faculty members, who are actively engaged in research and in training students to become proficient researchers, perceive that there is still potential to further develop the research capabilities of students. Thus, with the vision to become a leading research university, faculty members must maximize their training and competencies to be able to fully extend their expertise in research to the students. To develop the research capabilities applicable to undergraduate and even postgraduate students, Hughes [25] recommended the establishment of ongoing and discrete research skills support programs and/or embedding research

development in a taught program. The latter is already implemented in ISU-CBAPA through the inclusion of a research methodology course in the different programs offered.

Table 8. Perceptions on VMGO attainability through the development of research capabilities and competencies

Item	Students n=602	DI	Alumni n=54	DI	Faculty n=31	DI	Non-teaching n=48	DI	Weighted mean	DI
1. ISU-CBAPA enriches students in research methodologies, statistics, and research writing	4.56	TVGE	4.43	TVGE	3.97	TGE	4.29	TVGE	4.32	TVGE
2. ISU-CBAPA promotes the culture of research and creative work in its curricular offerings	4.57	TVGE	4.35	TVGE	4.00	TGE	4.31	TVGE	4.32	TVGE
3. ISU-CBAPA produces students as self-directed researchers in their areas of specialization or fields of expertise	4.54	TVGE	4.41	TVGE	3.80	TGE	4.17	TGE	4.24	TVGE
4. ISU-CBAPA keeps quality research performance or reputation	4.58	TVGE	4.44	TVGE	4.10	TGE	4.25	TVGE	4.36	TVGE
5. ISU-CBAPA develops research-related capabilities	4.59	TVGE	4.39	TVGE	3.90	TGE	4.19	TGE	4.28	TVGE
Overall mean	4.57	TVGE	4.40	TVGE	3.95	TGE	4.24	TVGE	4.30	TVGE

Note: Descriptive interpretation (DI); 1 to 1.80: To no extent (TNE); 1.81 to 2.60: To a slight extent (TSLE); 2.61 to 3.40: To some extent (TSOE); 3.41 to 4.20: To a great extent (TGE); 4.21 to 5.00: To a very great extent (TVGE)

3.3.3. Readiness for employment and/or managing a business

Table 9 disclosed that the students, alumni, and non-teaching perceive that ISU-CBAPA VMGO is being attained through students' readiness for employment and/or managing a business post-graduation to a very great extent, while the faculty perceives it only to a great extent. This indicates that ISU can achieve its target of preparing the students for employment and/or readiness for entrepreneurial business endeavors [33]. Nonetheless, it can be observed that faculty members exhibit a relatively lower regard towards the preparedness of students for employment post-graduation, which may be attributed from their academic role which allows them to directly evaluate the capabilities of the students based on their school performance.

Table 9. Perceptions on VMGO attainability through readiness for employment and/or managing a business

Item	Students n=602	DI	Alumni n=54	DI	Faculty n=31	DI	Non-teaching n=48	DI	Weighted mean	DI
1. ISU-CBAPA prepares students to be capable professionals or business owners in their field of work or duties and responsibilities.	4.56	TVGE	4.44	TVGE	4.13	TGE	4.40	TVGE	4.38	TVGE
2. ISU-CBAPA equips students with acquired workforce flexibility	4.54	TVGE	4.48	TVGE	3.94	TGE	4.33	TVGE	4.32	TVGE
3. ISU-CBAPA allows students to go the extra mile in preparation for their intended profession	4.57	TVGE	4.46	TVGE	3.87	TGE	4.40	TGE	4.32	TVGE
4. ISU-CBAPA produces competent students who spur and sustain leadership and innovation	4.58	TVGE	4.41	TVGE	4.03	TGE	4.33	TVGE	4.34	TVGE
5. ISU-CBAPA produces capable and performing students with chances for promotion and career advancement	4.58	TVGE	4.44	TVGE	4.19	TGE	4.35	TGE	4.39	TVGE
Overall mean	4.56	TVGE	4.45	TVGE	4.03	TGE	4.36	TVGE	4.35	TVGE

Note: Descriptive interpretation (DI); 1 to 1.80: To no extent (TNE); 1.81 to 2.60: To a slight extent (TSLE); 2.61 to 3.40: To some extent (TSOE); 3.41 to 4.20: To a great extent (TGE); 4.21 to 5.00: To a very great extent (TVGE)

This implies that faculty members have a significant impact on the students' preparation for their future careers. Coaching about career-related discussions such as the labor market and employer requirements can facilitate the students' transition to employment [28] and such faculty-student interaction,

particularly when engaged emotionally, can affect the self-perceived employability of students [26]. Institution-wise, the academe should consider in their curriculum revision the constructs (i.e. Career interest, self-ability, career motivation, career prospect, career path, career type, and career description) as interventions on the development of the students' career since they do not only begin their career after graduation but started during the pursuit of their degrees [29]. Additional input in the curriculum would also be the honing of personality traits of the students since this will lead them to become entrepreneurs [30].

3.4. Comparison of the stakeholders' awareness, awareness of dissemination, understanding, acceptance, congruency, and attainability of the ISU-CBAPA VMGO

As shown in Table 10, the various stakeholders do not significantly differ statistically ($p>0.05$) in terms of their awareness of the dissemination of ISU-CBAPA VMGO, which is consistent with the other findings [8]. Statistically significant differences ($p<0.05$) were found, however, on the group of respondent's awareness; understanding and acceptance; congruency of educational practices, strategies, and activities to ISU-CBAPA VMGO; and attainability.

Table 10. Analysis of variance on the respondents' awareness, awareness on dissemination, understanding and acceptance, congruency, and attainability of the ISU-CBAPA VMGO

		Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Awareness	Between groups	6.150	3	2.050	6.365	.000
	Within groups	235.469	731	.322		
	Total	241.620	734			
Awareness on dissemination	Between groups	2.195	3	.732	1.850	.137
	Within groups	289.018	731	.395		
	Total	291.213	734			
Understanding and acceptance	Between groups	2.666	3	.889	3.323	.019
	Within groups	195.509	731	.267		
	Total	198.175	734			
Congruency	Between groups	3.024	3	1.008	3.247	.021
	Within groups	226.948	731	.310		
	Total	229.972	734			
Attainability	Between groups	5.709	3	1.903	6.154	.000
	Within groups	226.037	731	.309		
	Total	231.746	734			

Further post-hoc analyses revealed a non-significant variation among respondents in terms of congruency but confirmed notable variances ($p<0.05$) in terms of awareness, understanding and acceptability, and attainability. Based on pairwise comparisons via Games-Howell, significant variances are confirmed between the faculty respondents and the other groups in their awareness of ISU-CBAPA VMGO as evidenced by $p<0.05$. Table 2 have shown that the faculty members have the highest level of awareness in terms of the mean score compared to other stakeholders, which is logical because of their crucial role in the implementation of the VMGO with direct involvement to students and other clientele. The Games-Howell pairwise comparison indicated statistically significant differences ($p=0.006$) between the faculty and non-teaching respondents in their understanding and acceptance of ISU-CBAPA VMGO, which may stem from their level of involvement. Similarly, the non-teaching personnel's view significantly differs with that of the students in terms of the attainability of ISU-CBAPA VMGO as confirmed through a Games Howell pairwise comparison with $p=0.021$. As shown in Table 4, the discrepancy is more evident in terms of the CBAPA goals and its programs' objectives due to the fact that, unlike the faculty members and students who are exclusively affiliated with CBAPA, a significant proportion of the non-teaching personnel included in this study were drawn from various non-academic offices where they are more focused on their administrative roles and support services [22].

3.5. Comparison of the stakeholders' perception of the attainability of the ISU-CBAPA VMGO based on three purposes

Table 11 indicates a significant difference through a one-way ANOVA analysis in the attainment of ISU-CBAPA VMGO in terms of the development of professional expertise; the development of research capabilities and competencies; and readiness for employment and/or managing a business with $p<0.05$. Post hoc analyses using the Scheffé test confirmed that the faculty and students differ significantly in their perceptions of developing professional expertise ($p=0.002$) and in developing research capabilities and competencies ($p=0.000$). Significant differences in the development of research capabilities were also confirmed via a Scheffé test between faculty and alumni ($p=0.002$), as well as between students and non-teaching ($p=0.000$). Regarding work readiness, Games-Howell was necessitated due to a violation of the

homogeneity of variances at $p=0.009$ as revealed in a Levene's test. The findings indicate a statistically significant difference between faculty members and all other groups, with a significance level of $p<0.05$.

It is noteworthy that the faculty's perception of the extent to which students develop professional expertise did not significantly differ from that of all other respondents, except for the students themselves. Despite students' belief that they have acquired the essential professional skills and research capabilities and feel prepared to enter the workforce thus inferring the fulfillment of the VMGO, the faculty, who are responsible for teaching and evaluating students' performance, argue that there is still room for improvement. Similarly, the alumni may have also assumed that the research they have learned at the university was very adequate as well as felt that they were fully equipped to be employed after graduation, contrary to the assessment of the faculty. However, the non-teaching staff believed that students' research capabilities were not fully developed, indicating a disagreement with the students' perception of their own research abilities. In terms of readiness to work, the faculty differs in its perception of the attainment of VMGO against the perceptions of the students, alumni, and non-teaching staff. Generally, these findings have shown that the faculty significantly differ in their perceptions in contrast with the others. Although still favorable, their perceptions suggest that ISU-CBAPA can still maximize its VMGO attainability. Given their pivotal role in attaining the VMGO, the faculty may perceive the necessity of improving the implemented strategies, programs, and activities in ISU-CBAPA that may lead to students' improvement which consequently impacts the accomplishment of the university's aspirations [31]. These may encompass augmenting student-faculty interaction [26] and refining the curriculum by designing relevant course materials, incorporating research development programs, and facilitating more career-related discussions [28] that will make the attainment of VMGO more significant when the students transition to the professional sphere.

Table 11. Analysis of variance on the attainability of the ISU-VMGO based on three purposes

		Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
1. Develop professional expertise	Between groups	5.960	3	1.987	6.557	.000
	Within groups	221.481	731	.303		
	Total	227.441	734			
2. Development of research capability and competencies	Between groups	15.558	3	5.186	15.436	.000
	Within groups	245.588	731	.336		
	Total	261.146	734			
3. Readiness for employment and/or managing a business	Between groups	10.016	3	3.339	13.333	.000
	Within groups	183.040	731	.250		
	Total	193.056	734			

4. CONCLUSION

In pursuit of continuous development and improvement of higher education institutions, planned organizational directions must consistently be assessed and in coordination with the stakeholders. Thus, the Isabela State University's vision and mission statements, the CBAPA goals, and programs' objectives were examined leading to the attainment of students' professional expertise, research competencies, and readiness to work after graduation. The research findings imply the extreme awareness of students and alumni stakeholders on the existence of VMGO where it was extensively disseminated and comprehended with widespread acceptance. Faculty members and the non-teaching staff, however, expressed a lesser degree of awareness which suggests that linkages to various industries, agencies institutions, regional industry sectors, and communities should be continuously established, maintained, and strengthened for better dissemination of the VMGO to its clientele.

On the other hand, the findings of high congruency of VMGO on the academic strategies, practices, and activities imply that the ISU-CBAPA is in the right direction toward its targeted outcomes which shows that it can achieve its strategic purpose effectively. Regarding the attainment of the VMGO, all stakeholders perceived that they were fully governed by the ISU-CBAPA VMGO principles. In terms of enhancing students' competencies, research capabilities, and employment readiness as the VMGOs chief upshot, the faculty members perceive the necessity of improving the implemented strategies, programs, and activities of ISU-CBAPA that will eventually lead to students' enhancement which consequently impacts the accomplishment of the university's aspirations. A longitudinal study may therefore be warranted for the institution to periodically monitor lapses and improvements relative to its VMGO. Future research studies may also opt to consider other statistical methods such as structural equation modeling (SEM) to further explore structural relationships among multiple factors that may influence the stakeholders' awareness, acceptance, congruence, and attainability of an academic institution's VMGO.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the Isabela State University for the support and encouragement given in the pursuit of R&D accomplishments.

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